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Subsurface Investigation for Infrastructural Development in Anaocha, Anambra State Southeast Nigeria, Using Electrical Resistivity Method

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ABSTRACT

This research employed electrical resistivity vertical sounding to probe the subsurface to ensure development of sustainable infrastructure on geologic materials across the study area. Apparent resistivity data generated from the field data were plotted against the electrode spacing to produce 2D profiles which reveals the layer configurations for each location. The percentage ratio distribution across the research zone reflects a complex geological settings and has a direct consequence on infrastructural development within the area. From the result acquired, 4 to 6 rock layers and their corresponding thickness, depth and rock types were identified. The layers include clayey, sandy, clayey sand, water saturated and faulted zones were identified. The result is crucial to developers for identification of subsurface features that could impair sustainable development of engineering structures.

Keywords: Vertical Electrical Sounding, Building Collapse, Apparent Resistivity, Competent Rock, Weathered Layer and Win-resistivity Plots.

INTRODUCTION

Subsurface investigation is an essential procedure before any infrastructural development project. It entails acquisition of information about the subsurface conditions such as lithological composition, geological structures, and groundwater distribution (Mgbolu et al, 2024). The information is required for sustainable designing and constructions.

Structural failure and collapse could result from the nature of the subsoil, undetected near-surface/subsurface geological structures, features induced by anthropogenic activities or inhomogeneity in soils and geomaterials constituting the foundation (Akintorinwa *et al.*, 2011), and such anomalous features are amenable to geophysical delineation. All infrastructural development are sited on earth materials. Investigating the subsurface at a proposed site to ascertain fitness of the host earth materials is important prior to the design of such structures (Olorunfemi *et al.*, 2004).

Engineering Infrastructures had remained poor for a number of reasons some of which are; poor construction materials, bad design, poor drainage network, geological factors, abandon river channels, high water table, water flooding and mechanical factors. Geological factors are rarely considered as precipitators of structural failure even though building foundations are founded on geologic materials

(Aigbedion, 2007; Momoh et al., 2008). Failures are not limited to any particular geologic setting, failures have been recorded on basement complex and sedimentary formations. These failures have been attributed to a number of factors such as inadequate information about the soil and the nature of the subsurface geologic materials. Hence, subsurface investigation should be considered before any infrastructural development (Adiat et al. 2009).

Location and Geological Setting the Study Area

The study covered 10 towns – Aguluzigbo, Agulu, Neni, Ichida, Adazi-Ani, Adazi-Enu, Adazi-Nnukwu, Akwaeze, Nri, and Obeledu in Anaocha Local Government Area, Anambra State, Southeast Nigeria. Geographically, Anaocha is positioned within 6° 12' 25"N latitude and 7° 04' 04"E longitude, bordering Dunukofia to the north, Njikoka to the west, and Awka North to the southwest (Akujieze et al., 2007). Anaocha covered an approximate land area of 171.62 km². The study area has diverse landscape as hills, valleys, and plains, spanning approximately 263.7 km². Anaocha Local Government Area (LGA), situated in Anambra State, Southeast Nigeria, lies within the Anambra Basin, a sedimentary basin formed during the Late Cretaceous to Paleogene period. The area is underlain by the Eocene-aged Bende-Ameki Group, comprising shale, sandstone, and siltstone, shaped by structural features such as faults, folds, and fractures, influencing the region's geomorphology and groundwater flow patterns (Fig. 1). The area's hydrogeological setting is characterized by a combination of dendritic and trellised drainage patterns, reflecting the underlying geology and structural controls. The region's topography is undulating, with varying elevations and landforms shaped by geological, tectonic, and erosional processes. The area's hills, valleys, and plains create a mosaic of landscapes. Anaocha LGA experiences a humid tropical climate, with high temperatures, abundant rainfall, and relatively consistent humidity levels throughout the year. The climate is classified as tropical wet and dry under the climate classification system, with a rainy season typically extending from March to October, and peak rainfall occurring between June and August. The region's tropical rainforest vegetation is characterized by a rich diversity of plant species, including African oil palm, rubber tree, and iroko.

Fig. 1: Stratigraphic succession in the Anambra and Niger Delta Basins

METHODOLOGY

Field data were acquired using electrical resistivity method, specifically vertical electrical sounding (VES), for subsurface investigation in the infrastructural development. The electrical sounding method utilized an ABEM Terrameter SAS 1000 current transmitter connected to an ammeter and voltmeter, clipped to a power source. The system's accessories, including a wire reel with electrical wires, were connected to probes that injected current into the subsurface. During surveying, coordinates and elevation of field locations were measured using the Global Positioning System. The 20 VES data acquired ranged from 2 locations per each town in the study area. The acquired data were processed and interpreted to generate resistivity models, revealing subsurface structures essential for infrastructure developmental work. Fig. 2 represent the study area and the VES locations acquired.

Fig. 2: Map of Anambra State and Topographic Map modelled with ArcGIS Software, showing the Study Area and VES points overlaid on the geological map are important for creating a resistivity profile.

Table 1: Anaocha Local Government Table of Location and Georeferenced Points
Anambra Central Senatorial Zone

LO CA TIO N	VES NO.	TO WN	LO NGI TU DE	LAT ITU DE	ELE VA TIO N	FO RM ATI O
Igweamaka Primary School Aguluzigbo	VES 1	Aguluzigbo	E007 ⁰ 02'. 008"	N06 ⁰ 16'. 369"	55	Ben de Am eki
Nduani Aguluzigbo	VES 2		E007 ⁰ 07'. 468"	N06 ⁰ 15'. 769"	51	
Umuowelle Agulu	VES 3	Agulu	E007 ⁰ 04'. 107"	N06 ⁰ 03'. 933"	108	
Roni Farms Ltd Agulu	VES 4	Agulu	E007 ⁰ 01'. 916"	N06 ⁰ 08'. 515"	121	
St. Mary's Catholic Church Umunri Neni	VES 5	Neni	E006 ⁰ 59'. 753"	N06 ⁰ 05'. 920"	197	
Umudioka Village Neni	VES 6	Neni	E006 ⁰ 59'. 475"	N06 ⁰ 04'. 384"	259	
Umuru Adazi –Ani	VES 7		E006 ⁰ 59'. 387"	N06 ⁰ 05'. 206"	230	
Umuru Viilage Adazi - Ani	VES 8	Adazi - Ani	E006 ⁰ 59'. 237"	N06 ⁰ 05'. 126"	251	
Obeagu Nri	VES 9	Nri	E007 ⁰ 01'. 384"	N06 ⁰ 08'. 442"	149	
Uruofolo Village Nri	VES 10		E007 ⁰ 01'. 119"	N06 ⁰ 08'. 153"	165	
Adazi- Nnukwu	VES 11	Adazi- Nnukwu	E007 ⁰ 01'. 064"	N06 ⁰ 06'. 158"	171	
Adazi Nnukwu	VES 12		E007 ⁰ 01'. 557"	N06 ⁰ 06'. 158"	203	
Akwaeze	VES 13	Akwaeze	E007 ⁰ 01'. 974"	N06 ⁰ 04'. 481"	274	
Akwaeze	VES 14		E007 ⁰ 00'. 964"	N06 ⁰ 03'. 742"	291	
Obeleduani Village Obeledu	VES 15	Obeledu	E007 ⁰ 01'.130"	N06 ⁰ 05'. 258"	196	
Ezele Village Obeledu	VES 16	Obeledu	E007 ⁰ 00'. 921"	N06 ⁰ 04'. 992"	226	
Ihuana Village	VES 17	Adazi-Enu	E006 ⁰ 59'. 304"	N06 ⁰ 03'. 723"	293	
Adazi-Enu	VES 18	Adazi-Enu	E006 ⁰ 59'. 475"	N06 ⁰ 04'. 384"	259	
Uburu Ichida	VES 19	Ichida	E007 ⁰ 59'. 206"	N06 ⁰ 01'. 657"	277	
Ichida	VES 20	Ichida	E007 ⁰ 58'. 368"	N06 ⁰ 04'. 549"	252	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interpretation of VES Data for Infrastructural Development in the Study Area.

The 20 Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) locations in Anaocha were modeled using WinResistivity software, revealing subsurface layering and lithologies. Each layer's resistivity, depth, thickness, and curve characteristics were tabulated. The modeled profiles showed distinct curve characteristics that

differentiated the layers, defined by their respective resistivity values. The thickness and depth of each layer were determined using modeled resistivity numbers, while the undetermined thickness was calculated as the product of the immediate layer thickness and depth. Resistograms were plotted using Win-Resistivity software, representing the apparent resistivity against current electrodes (AB/2) for each location. Histograms statistically presented the curve types, frequency, and percentage occurrence for each location. The interpreted layers are presented in Table 2, providing information of the subsurface for infrastructural development in Anaocha. Table 2 represent interpreted layers of VES 1-20 locations in Anaocha Local Government Area while the plots of curve type frequency and percentage occurrence in Anaocha surveyed locations is presented in fig.3.

Table 2: Interpreted Layers of VES 1 -20 y and percentage (in Anaocha Local Government Area				
Station ID/ Layers	App Res (Ωm)	Thickness (m)	Depth (m)	Description
VES 1(IGWUAMAKA PRIMARY SCHOOL AGULUZIGBO) (RMS: 2.2%)				CURVE TYPE KHK(ρ1< ρ2> ρ3< ρ4>ρ5)
1	2517.0	1.2	1.2	Top layer/Laterite
2	9205.0	1.3	2.5	Siltsand
3	348.9	2.7	5.2	Shalysand
4	14954.0	34.7	39.9	Sandstone
5	3284.0	Undetermined	74.6	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 2(NDUANI AGULUZIGBO) (RMS: 1.0%)				CURVE TYPE AAK((ρ1< ρ2< ρ3< ρ4>ρ5)
1	494.0	1.2	1.2	Top layer/Laterite
2	1135.0	4.0	5.2	Shalysand
3	6116.0	5.6	10.8	Siltsand
4	1922.0	11.6	22.4	Shalysand
5	7389.0	74.0	96.3	Sandstone
6	4243.0	Undetermined	170.3	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 3(UMUOWELLE AGULU) (RMS: 0.4%)				CURVE TYPE QHA(ρ1>ρ2> ρ3< ρ4<ρ5)
1	292.4	1.2	1.2	Top layer/Laterite
2	255.7	4.0	5.2	Shalysand
3	407.7	5.6	10.8	Siltsand
4	91.5	35.6	46.4	Shale
5	143.1	49.9	96.3	Water-Saturated Sand
6	722.6	Undetermined	146.2	Sandstone
VES 4(RONI FARMS LTD AGULU) (RMS:0.8%)				CURVE TYPE KA(ρ1< ρ2> ρ3<ρ4)
1	457.0	6.3	6.3	Top layer/Laterite
2	1089.0	5.7	12.0	Sandstone
3	8.9	36.5	48.5	Shale
4	50.8	Undetermined	85.0	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 5(ST.MARY CATHOLIC CHURCH UMUNRI NENI) (RMS: 1.5%)				CURVE TYPE AQ((ρ1< ρ2< ρ3>ρ4)

1	1133.0	3.3	3.3	Top layer/Laterite
2	1964.0	16.8	20.1	Siltsand
3	13607.0	26.7	46.8	Water-Saturated Sand
4	12.7	Undetermined	73.5	Shale
VES 6(UMUDIOKA VILLAGE NENI) (RMS: 0.9%)				CURVE TYPE QHA($\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	202.6	0.8	0.8	Top layer/Laterite
2	26.0	3.2	4.0	Shalysand
3	8.5	4.3	8.2	Shale
4	46.8	46.1	54.4	Shalysand
5	181.0	Undetermined	100.5	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 7 (UMURU AMAZI-ANI) (RMS: 1.8%)				CURVE TYPE AKH($\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	367.0	0.9	0.9	Top layer/Laterite
2	1271.0	6.3	7.2	Shalysand
3	3214.0	36.2	43.4	Siltsand
4	11094.0	43.8	87.2	Sandstone
5	937.0	84.6	171.8	Water-Saturated Sand
6	19000.0	Undetermined	256.4	Sandstone
VES 8(UMURU VILLAGE ADAZI-ANI) (RMS:2.5%)				CURVE TYPE HA($\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4$)
1	276.3	3.5	3.5	Top layer/Laterite
2	5894.7	6.2	9.7	Sandstone
3	4340.0	27.5	37.3	Siltsand
4	10607.2	Undetermined	64.8	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 9(OBEAGU) (RMS:1.3%)				CURVE TYPE KHA($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	405.0	1.2	1.2	Top layer/Laterite
2	13328.0	3.4	4.6	Sandstone
3	1429.0	16.9	21.5	Siltsand
4	213.0	146.0	167.5	Water-Saturated Sand
5	14225.0	Undetermined	313.5	Sandstone
VES 10(URUOFOLO VILLAGE NRI) (RMS: 1.3%)				CURVE TYPE KHA($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	112.0	2.0	2.0	Top layer/Laterite
2	1153.0	2.8	4.8	Sandstone
3	97.4	24.9	29.7	Shalysand
4	12.1	81.4	111.1	Shale
5	2554.0	Undetermined	192.5	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 11(ADAZI-NNUKWU) (RMS: 1.1%)				CURVE TYPE HK($\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4$)
1	62.4	0.8	0.8	Top layer/Laterite
2	18.7	9.5	10.3	Shale
3	348.0	11.4	21.7	Sandstone
4	10.2	Undetermined	33.1	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 12(ADAZI NNUKWU) (RMS: 1.0%)				CURVE TYPE HA($\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4$)
1	221.0	1.6	1.6	Top layer/Laterite
2	56.4	13.2	14.8	Shale
3	586.0		257.8	Water-Saturated Sand
4	13856.0	243.0 Undetermined	500.8	Sandstone

VES 13(AKWAEZE)					CURVE TYPE
(RMS: 1.7%)					AKH($\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	1326.9	1.0	1.0		Top layer/Laterite
2	1677.4	2.7	3.6		Siltsand
3	1458.6	5.0	8.6		Shalysand
4	4189.2	17.8	26.4		Sandstone
5	17528.6	29.7	56.1		Water-Saturated Sand
6	2956.6	Undetermined	85.8		Sandstone
VES 14 (AKWAEZE) (RMS: 1.9%)					CURVE TYPE
					KA($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$)
1	120.4	2.5	2.5		Top layer/Laterite
2	333.4	7.6	10.2		Siltsand
3	50949.4	31.0	41.1		Sandstone
4	868.3	Undetermined	72.1		Water-Saturated Sand
VES 15(OBELEDUANI VILLAGE OBELEDU)					CURVE TYPE
(RMS: 3.1%)					AKH($\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	164.1	1.0	1.0		Top layer/Laterite
2	926.0	1.5	2.6		Shalysand
3	54786.1	4.7	7.2		Sandstone
4	20312.1	9.7	17.0		Siltsand
5	304.8	31.3	48.3		Shale
6	41478.0	Undetermined	78.6		Water-Saturated Sand
VES 16(EZELE VILLAGE OBELEDU)					CURVE TYPE
(RMS: 1.4%)					KA($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$)
1	283.0	2.4	2.4		Top layer/Laterite
2	20293.0	4.4	6.7		Sandstone
3	843.9	18.4	25.1		Siltsand
4	7130.0	Undetermined	43.5		Water-Saturated Sand
VES 17(IHUANA VILLAGE)					CURVE TYPE
(RMS: 1.0%)					QHA($\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	2767.0	0.8	0.8		Top layer/Laterite
2	427.0	0.8	1.6		Shalysand
3	2091.0	1.7	3.3		Sandstone
4	630.0	4.9	8.2		Siltsand
5	6005.0	Undetermined	13.1		Water-Saturated Sand
VES 18 (ADAZI-ENU) (RMS: 3.0%)					CURVE TYPE
					AKH($\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	507.2	0.9	0.9		Top layer/Laterite
2	2152.3	10.2	11.1		Siltsand
3	19950.0	24.9	36.1		Sandstone
4	2537.7	60.9	96.9		Water-Saturated Sand
5	64993.2	Undetermined	157.8		Sandstone
VES 19(UBURU ICHIDA)					CURVE TYPE
(RMS: 3.8%)					AHA($\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	32.7	0.9	0.9		Top layer/Laterite
2	3066.5	3.5	4.5		Shalysand
3	16573.6	21.6	26.1		Siltsand
4	33814.5	25.8	51.8		Sandstone

5	865.0	12.0	63.9	Water-Saturated Sand
6	79729.2	Undetermined	75.9	Sandstone
VES 20(ICHIDI) (RMS: 3.0%)				CURVE TYPE HKA($\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	1071.9	1.5	1.5	Top layer/Laterite
2	269.0	1.4	2.9	Shale
3	38032.0	7.0	9.8	Sandstone
4	3505.0	27.8	37.6	Siltsand
5	52963.4	Undetermined	65.4	Water-Saturated Sand

Fig. 3: Shows Curve Type Frequency and Percentage Occurrence in Anaocha Surveyed Locations. Integrated Interpretation of VES Locations of Anaocha L.G.A and Implications for Infrastructure Development:

The geoelectric layer across the study generally reveals four to six layers characterized by mostly topsoil which are mostly laterite, sandstone, water saturated sand, shale, and shaley sand. The geological characteristics of each layer have varying implications for infrastructure development which is very significant for proper foundation design. Foundation design should account for the varying subsurface conditions. The predominant rock types revealed by the results and their implication to infrastructural development are;

Top layer/Laterite: The presence of laterite at shallow depths can provide a stable foundation for light structures but may pose challenges for deep-foundation construction. This material can be excavated and used as a construction material for road base and embankment fill.

Shaley sand: The suitability of shaley sand for infrastructure development depends on their specific properties. These materials can exhibit a mix of properties inherited from silt, sand, and shale, which could impact their bearing capacity and settlement characteristics.

Shale: Shale formations generally have low permeability and can be suitable for supporting infrastructure, but their strength and stability should be evaluated for specific construction projects.

Water-Saturated Sand: The presence of water-saturated sand should be carefully considered in infrastructure development, especially in terms of foundation design and groundwater control measures. This layer can provide challenges for infrastructure development due to potential issues such as settlement, liquefaction, and water seepage.

Sandstone: Sandstone is a sedimentary rock with varying strength, durability, and weathering properties. The suitability of this layer for infrastructure development depends on its mechanical properties, such as compressive strength, tensile strength, and fracture density.

Figure 4: (i) Representative computer software plot of apparent resistivity data from VES 1 at Igwuamaka Primary School, Aguluzigbo. (ii) Geologic section delineated from the interpretation of the geo-electric section.

Figure 5: (i) Representative computer software plot of apparent resistivity data from VES 6 at Umudoka Village Neni. (ii) Geologic section delineated from the interpretation of the geo-electric section.

Evaluation of parameters from VES interpretation for Engineering

From the VES interpretation of the modelled layers, the following parameters as; depth to competent rocks (m), Thickness of weathered zones and depth to weathered zones were calculated to evaluate the subsurface sustainability for engineering infrastructure in the study area. Thickness of weathered zones is the thickness of layers considered as weathered zones while weathered zones are the weak zones in the modelled profile of apparent resistivity and current electrodes. Depth to weathered zones is the depth of the bottom of the weathered zones by adding the thickness of the weathered zones to the depth of the topmost layer.

Table 3: Parameters from VES Interpretation for Infrastructural Development in Anaocha Local Government

VES NO.	<i>Aquifer App. Res (Ωm)</i>	<i>Depth to Competent Rocks (m)</i>	<i>Thickness of Weathered Zones (m)</i>	<i>Depth to Weathered Zones (m)</i>
VES 1	3284.0	41.6	12.5	0.8
VES 2	4243.0	22.8	16.9	3.3
VES 3	143.1	64.3	11.3	6.3
VES 4	50.8	178.9	14.7	2.0
VES 5	13607.0	53.2	6.2	1.2
VES 6	181.0	37.9	1.5	2.4
VES 7	937.0	76.9	2.6	1.5
VES 8	10607.2	219.5	3.1	1.4
VES 9	213.0	59.0	1.9	344.8
VES 10	2554.0	203.1	5.6	357.1
VES 11	10.2	178.9	1.8	176.8
VES 12	586.0	74.7	2.9	689.7
VES 13	17528.6	74.4	0	1052.6
VES 14	868.3	74.4	5.9	232.9
VES 15	41478.0	54.6	0.7	606.1
VES 16	7130.0	82.7	0.89	416.7
VES 17	6005.0	96.8	4.1	6.4
VES 18	2537.7	111.3	6.7	1.3
VES 19	865.0	98.7	8.4	2.8
VES 20	52963.4	53.4	9.3	4.8

Map Interpretation of Evaluated Parameters for Anaocha Local Government

Area

Fig. 6: Apparent Resistivity Map of Anaocha Local Government Area

Low Apparent Resistivity Zones ($\rho_a < 18k\Omega m$)

The low apparent resistivity zones, encompassing such as Aguluzigbo, Agulu, Neni, Adazi-Ani, Nri, Adazi-Nnukwu, Akwaeze, Adazi-Enu, and Ichida (VES 1-12, 14, 17-19) are characterized by high conductivity materials such as saturated clays and saline groundwater. Interpretation of these zones reveals a high likelihood of soil instability and corrosion due to the presence of aggressive groundwater. The low resistivity values indicate poor soil quality, making it challenging for infrastructural development. It Implications for infrastructural development in these zones include increased risks of foundation failure, soil settlement, and water damage. Structures built in these areas may require specialized foundation designs, waterproofing measures, and regular monitoring of groundwater levels.

Moderate Apparent Resistivity Zones ($18k\Omega m > \rho_a > 34k\Omega m$)

The moderate apparent resistivity zones are found in partly Akwaeze and Obeledu (VES 13, 16) are marked by intermediate conductivity materials such as sands and silty soils. Interpretation of these zones suggests a moderate risk of settlement and liquefaction due to the presence of loose soils.

Implications for infrastructural development in these zones include potential settlement and liquefaction hazards. Buildings and roads constructed in these areas may require shallow foundations with spread footings, compaction tests for soil stability, and careful consideration of drainage systems.

High Apparent Resistivity Zones ($\rho_a > 34k\Omega m$)

The high apparent resistivity zones, encompassing in partly Obeledu and Ichida (VES 15, 20) are characterized by low conductivity materials such as bedrock and unsaturated soils.

Interpretation of these zones reveals a low risk of soil instability and corrosion. The implications for infrastructural development in these zones include reduced risks of foundation failure and soil settlement. Structures built in these areas can utilize shallow foundations with spread footings, and water supply systems design should consider water availability and quality.

Fig. 7: Depth to Competent Rock Map of Anaocha Local Government Area

The depth to competent rock, which refers to the vertical distance from the ground surface to the top of a strong and stable bedrock, is a critical factor in assessing the suitability of geological formations for infrastructure development. Depth to Competent rocks identifies the depth at which strong, stable rocks suitable for bearing the weight of structures are found. Deeper competent rocks may increase construction costs. we consider three depth ranges:

Shallow Depth to Competent Rock Zones (16- 40meters): Areas (1,2,10,13 and 14)with shallow depths to competent rock are generally favorable for infrastructure development, as they provide a stable and strong foundation for structures. Shallow bedrock also reduces the need for deep excavations and extensive foundation work, resulting in lower construction costs and shorter project timelines. Structures built in these areas can utilize shallow foundations, and drainage systems can be designed with confidence.The respective location of the VES points are as follows Aguluzigbo,Partly Nri and Akwaeze.

Moderate Depth to Competent Rock Zones (40-60 meters): These zones(5,6,7,9,15,16,18 and 20) present a mix of advantages and challenges for infrastructure development. Construction in these areas may require deeper foundations or the use of specialized techniques to ensure the stability of structures. Understanding the geological characteristics of the bedrock, such as its composition, degree of fracturing, and weathering, is necessary for designing appropriate foundation systems and construction methodologies. The respective location of the VES point of these zones are Neni,partly Adazi-Ani,Partly Nri,Obeledu, Partly Adazi-Enu and Ichida.

Deep Depth to Competent Rock Zones (>60 meters): Areas(VES 3,4,8,11,12,17 and 19) with deep depths to competent rock pose significant challenges for infrastructure development. Construction in these zones typically requires extensive engineering interventions, such as deep foundations, advanced excavation methods, or ground improvement techniques, to ensure the structural integrity of buildings and other infrastructure. Assessing the geological characteristics and properties of the bedrock at these depths is vital for developing cost-effective and sustainable solutions for construction projects. The location of the respective VES are as follows Agulu,partlyAdazi-Ani,Adazi-Nnukwu,Partly Adazi-Enu and Ichida.

Fig. 8: Thickness of Weathered Layers Map of Anaocha Local Government Area

The thickness of the weathered zone, which refers to the upper layer of rock that has undergone physical and chemical alteration due to weathering processes, is a critical factor in assessing the suitability of geological formations for infrastructure development. Weathered rock materials may have reduced strength and durability compared to unweathered rock. The thickness of weathered zones impacts the stability of the ground and the need for engineered solutions.

Shallow Weathered Layers (1-8meters): Sites(5,6,7,8,9,13,14,15,16,17 and 18)with shallow weathered layers generally simplify access to competent bedrock for foundation support, making them advantageous for infrastructure development. However, these zones may require special attention to aspects like erosion, slope stability, and potential bedrock weathering, which could affect the performance of structures. Furthermore, the thin weathered layer might not provide enough cushioning for structures, potentially leading to increased foundation stress. The zones are located at Neni,Adazi Ani,Partly Nri,Akwaeze,Obeledu and Adazi Enu.

Moderately Weathered Layers (8-15 meters): These zones(1,2,3,4,11,19 and 20)pose both benefits and difficulties for infrastructure development. While a moderate depth of weathered layers can provide cushioning and decrease bedrock weathering, construction in these areas might require deeper foundations or ground improvement techniques for structural stability, particularly if weathered materials are weak or highly compressible. Comprehending the properties of weathered materials, including their composition, compaction, and hydraulic conductivity, is essential for designing suitable foundation systems and construction techniques. Here are the respective locations Aguluzigbo,Agulu,PartlyAdazi-Nnukwu and Ichida.

Thick Weathered Layers (>14 meters): Thick weathered layer zones (10 and 12) present considerable challenges for infrastructure development. Construction in these zones often demands substantial engineering interventions, such as deep foundations, advanced excavation methods, or ground improvement techniques, to ensure structural integrity. Evaluating geological characteristics and properties of weathered materials is vital for developing cost-effective and sustainable construction solutions. The location of the respective VES are Partly Nri and Adazi – Nnukwu.

Fig. 9: Depth of Weathered Layers Map of Anaocha Local Government Area

The depth to the weathered zone, which refers to the vertical distance from the ground surface to the top of the weathered rock layer, is a critical factor in assessing the suitability of geological formations for infrastructure development. Shallow weathered zones may require special design considerations or ground improvements to ensure the stability of the structures.

we consider three depth ranges:

Shallow Depth to Weathered Zones (0-2.5 meters): Areas(1,5,7,8,9,11,13,15,16 and 18) with shallow depths to the weathered zone are generally favorable for infrastructure development, competent bedrock are been identified and detailed for easier foundation support. However, these zones requires sufficient and efficient reconnaissance survey for the identification of necessary informations and factors such as erosion, slope stability, and the potential for bedrock weathering, which can impact the overall performance of structures. Additionally, the shallow weathered layer may not offer sufficient cushioning for structures, which can lead to higher stresses on the foundation. These zones are recognized at the location listed in respective order of the VES points Partly Aguluzigbo,partly Neni,Adazi-Ani,Partly (Adazi-Nnukwu,Akwaeze) ,Obeledu and Partly Adazi Enu.

Moderate Depth to Weathered Zones (2.5-4.5 meters): These zones(2,4,6,12,19 and 20)present an optional information for infrastructure development. The presence of a moderate depth to the weathered zone provides effects and reduce the effort for bedrock breakage. On the other hand, construction in these areas may require deeper and stronger laid foundations or ground improvement techniques to ensure the stability of structures, particularly if the weathered materials are weak or highly compressible. Understanding the properties of weathered materials, such as their composition, compaction, and hydraulic conductivity, is important for designing appropriate foundation systems and construction methodologies. Location of the VES points are attributed to the following places Partly(Aguluzigbo,Agulu,Neni) and Ichida.

Deep Depth to Weathered Zones (>4.5 meters): Areas(3,10,14 and 17)with deep depths to the weathered zone signifies problems for infrastructure development. Construction in these zones typically requires thorough geological survey and invention of expertise, such as deep foundations, advanced excavation methods, or ground improvement techniques, to ensure the structural integrity of buildings and other infrastructure. The VES points on the topographic map is location in Partly Agulu,Neni,Akwaeze and Adazi-Enu.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study emphasized the importance of considering subsurface conditions in infrastructural development. Subsurface investigation using Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) was utilized to characterize Aniocha area of Anambra State. The result revealed the different rock types underlying the area, this information is crucial for solid foundation design of the areas. The result is a valuable tool in assessing the suitability of sites for infrastructural development. By providing detailed information on the electrical resistivity of subsurface layers, The VES result can enable engineers to identify potential hazards, determine the depth of suitable foundations, and optimize the design of structures. The non-invasive nature and low cost of the technique make it a easy and replicable. This study is vital because it ensures infrastructures are developed on solid and reliable foundations, thereby enhancing their long-term durability and safety.

Disclaimer (Artificial intelligence)

Author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.) and text-to-image generators have been used during the writing or editing of this manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

Author(s) hereby declare that no conflict of interest in the writing of this paper.

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